

REVOLUTION

The cell generates electricity from hydroxide ions

Johan Nygren*

Independent researcher

“In the search for the miraculous, we find that it’s often right before our very eyes but we fail to see it. “

Introduction

There is one chemical reaction that releases electricity from water, $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$. Based on the benefit of being able to use water, that makes up 99% of all molecules in a cell, as fuel for an “engine” of life, the machinery of the cell is likely organized around extracting hydroxide ions as fuel for that reaction. Positive selection for turning water into fuel would mean that the basic building blocks of the cell are components of a “water refinery” machinery that formed the basis of life.

Cells refine H_2O into OH^- by excluding H^+

Water can be used as a fuel to produce electric current with the reaction $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$. This reaction is only favourable if the hydrogen ions that would tend to neutralize it are displaced. Given the benefits to the cell of being able to use water as fuel, the main argument being the extreme abundance of water in the cell, it can be predicted that the cell is built on the ability to exclude H^+ , in other words, to refine H_2O into OH^- . This theory of the cell as a “water refinery” is supported by that water tends to spontaneously exclude H^+ , if there is a scaffold that promotes the gel-phase of water, $(\text{H}_3\text{O}_2^-)_n$. This property exists in all gels (Pollack, 2013).

The inherent ability of gels to exclude H^+ is amplified if the gel (including the scaffold) prefers to associate with a monovalent cation other than H^+ , when other cations are available. In the cell, K^+ evidently fits the role of a substitute for the hydrogen ions that are displaced from the gel-phase water.

Using a separate cation to exclude H^+ in the medium outside the cell, the extracellular space, favours the release of the hydroxide fuel, since K^+ that stabilizes the gel is able to leave the cell along its concentration gradient. Na^+ fits the role of an H^+ substitute extracellularly.

Since the ability to burn water would be very beneficial to a machine that consists primarily of water, it can be predicted that K^+ and Na^+ substitute H^+ as the positive pole to the negatively charged H_3O_2^- gel of the cell (see Pollack, 2014), and that they are components of a “water refinery” machinery that forms the basis of life.

Figure 1 Molecular representation of the gel-phase of water, from Pollack, 2013.

Corresponding author: e-mail: johanngrn@gmail.com

K⁺ and Na⁺ as "water refinery" components

The cell's negative electrical potential of ~50–100 mV is a result of negatively charged gel-phase water that excludes hydrogen ions (Pollack, 2014). Monovalent cations other than H⁺ can substitute the conjugate ion to the gel-phase water, favouring the chemical reaction $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$. The "proto machinery" of the cell has likely evolved to refine water into hydroxide ions, providing the cell with abundant fuel for the "engine" of life.

If the cell has evolved to rely on intracellular K⁺ as a substitute for H⁺, then an increase in either cation should affect the distribution of the other. This is also what is observed, a mechanism often dubbed the "K/H exchanger". The theory that the cell has evolved to substitute H⁺ for K⁺ as the positive pole to the negatively charged H₃O₂⁻ gel of the cell, is a perfect explanation for K-H exchange. It provides an evolutionary and physiological imperative for why extracellular acidosis leads to a release of K⁺ from cells and thus hyperkalemia, and conversely why hyperkalemia leads to the exit of H⁺ from cells, resulting in extracellular acidosis.

Figure 2 The basic building blocks of the cell form a "water refinery" organized around extracting hydroxide ions as fuel.

Turning on the engine, depolarization

The theory that the cell evolved, at the most rudimentary level, to use hydroxide ions as fuel, provides a new lens for understanding the change of electrical potential associated with cell depolarization. Evolutionarily, the cell adapted to refine H₂O into OH⁻ by substituting H⁺

as the positive pole of the H₃O₂⁻ gel that forms around scaffolds like amino acid polymers. The resting state has a fully charged supply of the cell's fuel, hydroxide ions.

The cell is able to turn its engine on and off through the allosteric regulator ATP, that adjusts the ability of the protein scaffold to organize water into the gel-phase H₃O₂⁻ (Ling, 1962). ATP induces a protein conformation that holds the fuel supply in gel-phase. Switching off the resting state, by splitting ATP into ADP + P, releases the hydroxide ions from the fuel supply, and their electrical potential is discharged in the reaction $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$.

The origin of life, electrogenesis from water

"Nothing in biology makes sense except in the light of evolution."

Sidney Fox demonstrated in the 1960s that amino acid polymers boiled in water self-assemble into cells (Fox, 1965), and later showed experimentally in the 1980s that these cells selectively adsorbed K⁺ to concentrations up to 1600x that in the medium (Fox, 1981; Matveev, 2016). This ability for organic polymers like proteins to assemble into cells is not unique to proteins, polymer filaments in general order water into its fourth phase, (H₃O₂⁻)_n (Pollack, 2013). Gels form as a result of an inherent water-splitting ability of the scaffold it organizes around. *The act of a gel forming to begin with, is the first half of electrogenesis from water.*

That water electrogenesis was the basis of life is supported by that all gels catalyze the first half of the reaction $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$, all gels purify OH⁻ from H₂O. The cell could evolve by improving this base electrical potential of gels, through the use of monovalent cations that substituted H⁺. These "water refinery components" are evolutionarily conserved since the origin of life, like Ernest Baldwin wrote, "the ionic conditions under which cell life is possible are very restricted indeed, and have not changed substantially since life began." The homeostasis of potassium and sodium, the "water refinery ions" of the cell, are under tight control, in vertebrates coordinated via the endocrine system by aldosterone.

The theory that the cell evolved by positive selection for turning water into fuel is simple, and unifying. It provides a physical basis for life, electrogenesis from water, and integrates disparate themes from the past century of cell biology into a unified theory.

Figure 3 Cells store electrical potential in hydroxide ions, organized into a gel, and turn this abundant fuel into electricity in the reaction $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$.

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